

Electrodeposition of Co-Ni alloy from citrate-acetate bath on steel substrate

S. M. Rashwan* and H. E. Ibrahim

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt

E-mail : smrashwan2007@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Cobalt-nickel electrodeposition on steel substrate was carried out from solutions containing nickel sulfate, cobalt sulfate, sodium sulfate and sodium citrate and sodium acetate with 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 ratio respectively. The study dealt with the influence of bath composition, current density, pH, time of deposition, temperature and additives such as saccharin and thiourea on cathodic current efficiency. Throwing power and throwing index was calculated for the best bath for deposition. Also cyclic voltammograms was detected for the optimum bath composition. The efficiency for deposition from citrate-acetate mixed bath is higher than that reported for the separated citrate and acetate baths. The surface morphology of Ni-Co alloy was investigated by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) while the structure was studied by using X-ray diffraction analysis.

Keywords : Electrodeposition, cobalt-nickel alloy, citrate-acetate bath, steel substrate.

Cobalt-nickel alloys has been studied because of their high corrosion resistant as compared with the corresponding single metals¹. Cobalt-nickel alloys exhibit a spectrum of physical properties that have lead to the widespread use of these material in a variety of high-technology applications the recent emergence of microstructure and microsystems. Fabrication by electroplating through thick three-dimensional complex - shape electroformed mouldes illustrates the potential for new challenging applications of these alloys. Magnetic recording taps, composite coatings, and devices for photothermal conversion of solar energy are only a few examples of non-decorative uses of cobalt-nickel electrodeposition²⁻⁷. The magnetic, mechanical and corrosion properties of Ni-Co deposits are dictated by the structure and alloy composition. These parameters in turn are affected by processing variables such as plating-bath chemistry, pH, temperature, and applied current density. It is well established that the electrodeposition of iron-group alloys is followed by a local pH rise near the electrode surface. This pH rise is favored when H₂ is evolved simultaneously with alloy deposition⁸⁻¹³. This is explained by the surface precipitation and occlusion of hydroxides in the growing deposit resulting from an increase in the pH of the solution adjacent to the cathode (pHs). A near-electrode pH rise influences the reduction of cations that is supposed to be preceded by dehydration is decomposition of Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes. The importance of knowing the

surface concentration of the reacting species in the electrochemical reaction, including that of the hydronium ion in the near-electrode layer, was realized long ago^{14,15}.

Deposition of Co-Ni alloys with predictable properties therefore depends in large part on understanding the effect of electrode polarization and near-electrode phenomena. The kinetics of single iron-group metal deposition has been studied by many authors and excellent reviews are available^{8-12,16,17}. The deposition of cobalt is greatly favored over the deposition of nickel^{11,12,17,18-23}. This behavior, the opposite of that which would be predicted from thermodynamics alone ($E^0_{Ni^{2+}} = -0.23$ V and $E^0_{Co^{2+}} = -0.27$ V vs NHE), is known as anomalous codeposition. The anomalous behavior is represented by expectedly high cobalt content even at small fraction of the H₃O⁺ limiting current in different electrolytes⁸.

Experimental

Each experiment was carried out on fresh solutions, by dissolving request amount of salts in distilled water. For electrodeposition, a steel cathode and platinum sheet anode, both (dimensions 2.5 × 3.0 cm), were used. The plating cell used was a rectangular Perspex trough (10 × 3 cm) provided with vertical grooves, on each of the side walls, to fix the electrodes. Before each run, the steel cathode was mechanically polished with different grade paper emery paper (360, 800 and 1000) and then

washed with distilled water, rinsed with ethanol and weighed. Direct current was supplied by a d.c. power supply unit (25 V). The cathodic current efficiency (f) were determined with the help of a Cu-coulometer ($f = W_{\text{exp}}/W_{\text{th}}$), where W_{exp} is the weight of the deposit obtained experimentally and W_{th} is the weight of the deposit calculated theoretically according to Faraday's law.

The percentage throwing power (P_{throw}) of the solution was measured using a Haring-Blum rectangular Perspex cell (3.0 cm wide, 13.0 cm long, with 2.5 cm solution depth) fitted with an anode between two parallel steel cathodes where ratio of the far to near distance was varied from 1 : 1 to 3 : 1. This calculated from Field's formula²⁴ :

$$P_{\text{throw}} = \frac{L - m}{L + m + 2} \times 100$$

where L is the ratio of the cathode distance to the anode distance (far to near 1 to 3) and m is the ratio of the weight of the deposited metal on the near to the weight of the deposited on the far cathode. The value of m was measured as a function of L over a wide range of linear ratios varying between 1 : 1 and 3 : 1. The throwing index (I_{throw}) of each bath was considered as the reciprocal of the slope of the m against L plot^{25,26}.

The cyclic voltammetry measurements were recorded on a glassy carbon electrode starting from the open circuit potential to the more negative direction up to the anodic potential 0.5 V. The carbon electrode was polished with alumina before each run until mirror surface obtained, then washed several times with doubly distilled water. A potentiostat/galvanostat controlled by a computer were used for all electrochemical measurements. All potentials were measured relative to saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The surface morphology of the Co-Cr alloy electrodeposited on steel was examined using scanning electron microscopy (Jeol JEM 100S electron microscope). The crystalline structure of Co-Cr thin film deposited on steel from the optimum bath in absence and presence of additives was examined by X-ray diffraction using a Philips PW 1390 diffractometer.

Results and discussion

Nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complex formation with acetate and citrate anions was studied by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). The descending character of dependence of the relaxation efficiency indicates the formation of nickel acetate complexes. Linearity of the $K_{\text{el}}/C_{\text{Ac}}^2$ vs

K_{el} curve was found only for $n = 2$, where n is the number of ligand. This points to $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ complex composition. The value of pK for complex formation, calculating according Ref. 27, is 6.8 ± 0.8 . Nickel concentration independent k_{el} suggests the absence of binuclear complexes. Similarly, a $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ complex with pK 7.8 ± 0.8 . Citrate anions form a wide variety of complexes as a result of their three carboxyl and one hydroxyl groups. In addition, a feature peculiar to citrate nickel and cobalt complexes may be interelectron repulsion of the electron donating groups. This may be followed by the occurrence of a nonbonded carboxyl group capable protonation and surface coordination. The reactions of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with citric acid at high reagent concentrations as those used in industrial electrolytes and over a wide of solution acidity showed the formation of NiH_2Cit , NiHCit^- , $\text{Ni}_2\text{Cit}(\text{HCit})^{3-}$, $\text{Ni}_2\text{Cit}_2^{4-}$, CoH_2Cit^- , CoHCit^- , $\text{Co}_2\text{Cit}_2^{4-}$ complexes.

It was found also that species $\text{NiCo}(\text{HCitCit})^{3-}$ and $\text{NiCo}(\text{Cit})_2^{4-}$ at $\text{pH} > 6$ and 1 : 1 metal to citric acid concentrations. The pK values of those complexes were 19 and 27.7, respectively. In addition to, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$, $\text{Ni}(\text{Ac})_2$, $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$ and $\text{Co}(\text{Ac})_2$ complexes²⁸.

Current efficiency and composition of the deposits :

Fig. 1 : The content of cobalt is always higher than that expected from the cobalt concentration in the bath. At $C_{\text{Co}^{2+}} : C_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} = 1 : 4$, the deposit contain 45% cobalt, while at ratio of (1 : 1) the cobalt content was 94% at 25 °C and 0.8640 A dm². It was found that Ni-Co alloys have an unambiguous indication of the inhibition

Fig. 1(a). Effect of cobalt sulfate concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing nickel sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), $\text{pH} = 6$, current density (0.432 A dm⁻²), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

of deposition of the more noble metal and promotion of the deposition of the less noble metal. The data are in a good agreement with other authors²⁸.

While by increasing the concentration of the less noble metal, it decreases the cathodic current efficiency as it gives more chance for hydrogen evolution. But it is nearly having no effect on CCE% in case of higher concentration of citrate anions in the bath as shown in Fig. 1(b).

Fig. 1(b). Effect of cobalt sulfate concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing nickel sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), pH = 6, current density (0.432 A dm⁻²), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

Fig. 2 : As the net concentration of the cations increases, the alloy becomes enriched with cobalt, but either the bath is enriched with citrate or acetate, the CCE is nearly constant, having higher value when the bath

Fig. 2(a). Effect of nickel sulfate concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), pH = 6, current density (0.432 A dm⁻²), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

contain higher ratio of acetate due to acetate form less stable complex with cobalt and nickel than citrate, which give more chance for metals deposition.

Fig. 2(b). Effect of nickel sulfate concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), pH = 6, current density (0.432 A dm⁻²), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

Fig. 3 : At low current density, the increase in anions concentration in sulphate-based solution is followed by a sharp decrease in partial current efficiencies and, consequently, in the current efficiency of the nickel-cobalt alloys (by 99.9 to 72%, the maximum values in two cases). This may be (Table 1) explained by decreased activity of Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ cations in the presence of the high concentration of citrate as a complexing agent in the electro-

Fig. 3(a). Effect of current density on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

lyte. The increases in C_{Cit}^{4-} in the electrolyte have almost no influence on the alloy composition (in case of Cit : Ac = 1 : 2 cobalt in deposit is in range 88 to 92% and in case of Cit : Ac = 2 : 1 cobalt in deposition is in range 88 to 81%; mean no effective change). As the concentration of citrate anions increase cathodic polarization increase.

Fig. 3(b). Effect of current density on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (40 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 15 min and 25 °C.

Table 1. The distribution of complex nickel and cobalt citrate species at pH 3.5 and 8.2, calculated from NMR measurements²⁸

Nickel(II) and cobalt(II) citrate complexes	Relative concentration (%)	
	At pH = 3.5	At pH = 8.2
NiH ₂ Cit	16.7	0
NiHCit ⁻	20.5	3.4
Ni ₂ Cit(HCit) ³⁻	0	27.6
Ni ₂ Cit ₂ ⁴⁻	0	5.1
CoH ₂ Cit	56	0
NiHCit ⁻	36	1.1
CoCit ₂ ⁴⁻	0.3	98.9

However, at high current density (over 0.643 A dm⁻²) the coating become very bright and extremely brittle, so the cathodic current efficiency decreased.

In order to simulate the actual operating conditions, the concentrations of all possible nickel and cobalt species were calculated from the equilibrium equations. The distribution of complexes species with pH shown that, it is clear that above pH 4 CoHCit⁻ is prevalent cobalt species, and above pH 6 the concentration of binuclear co-

balt complexes dramatically increases. However, nickel, was found to be only partially bound by citrate and acetate anions.

Either citrate or acetate is the predominant complexing agent in solution as shown in Figs. 4(a,b), the formation of more stable complexes of nickel between pH 2 and 6 is followed by decrease in concentration of nonbonded citrate anions. This, in turn, shifts the equilibrium of the complexation reactions towards formation of as the cobalt aqua-complexes and current efficiency of cobalt in-

Fig. 4(a). Effect of pH on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²) and 25 °C.

Fig. 4(b). Effect of pH on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (40 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²) and 25 °C.

creases. In Ref. (27) the authors state that the inhibiting effect on the codeposition of the more noble metal is generally high when the reaction rate of the less noble metal is kinetically controlled, and it diminishes limiting current reached and also the total CCE increased.

As the pH is further raised, more stable complexes of both metal are formed which get their deposition in alloy more difficult so the CCE decreased. The quality of deposition in the vicinity of bulk pH 2.0 was unacceptable owing to rapid hydrogen evolution that interfered with regular crystal growth. This resulted in porous and dull deposits. At pH 2 to 4 the deposit become less stressed and the further pH rise didn't influence the quality of a the alloy.

Figs. 5(a,b) shows the effect of time on the current efficiency and composition of the alloy. It is clear that the efficiency increases and then tends to remain almost constant. In the same time the percentage of cobalt in deposits increases. Hydrogen evolution decreases with increasing plating time as a result of increasing pH in the vicinity of the cathode surface.

Figs. 6(a,b) shows that by increasing bath temperature the current efficiency increases due to the decrease in the limiting current of hydrogen evolution, while the composition of the alloy percentage of cobalt in deposit is nearly constant, so the nickel percentage increases is responsible for increasing in current efficiency as it is the more noble metal.

Fig. 5(a). Effect of deposition time on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 25°C .

Fig. 5(b). Effect of deposition time on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (40 gL^{-1}), current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 25°C .

Fig. 6(a). Effect of temperature on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}) and pH = 6.

Figs. 7(a,b) and 8(a,b) : The percentage of citrate and acetate in bath not effect on the deposition behavior in the presence of additives but the obtained current efficiencies in the baths that enriched with acetate is higher than that enriched with citrate due to the stability constants for cobalt and nickel complexes with acetate are less than that formed with citrate, so it is easier to give active ions for deposition.

Throwing power and throwing index of the bath :

The values of the percentage throwing power P_{throw}

Fig. 6(b). Effect of temperature on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (40 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}) and pH = 6.

Fig. 7(b). Effect of saccharin concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (40 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 25°C .

Fig. 7(a). Effect of saccharin concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 25°C .

Fig. 8(a). Effect of thiourea concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 45°C .

of the bath computed by Field's empirical formula at a distance ratio 1 : 3 were determined. Moreover, the throwing index I_{throw} were determined by plotting the metal distribution ratio m , and linear ratio (1 : 1 to 1 : 3) as

Fig. 8(b). Effect of thiourea concentration on the nickel percent in the alloy deposit during the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (40 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and 45°C .

shown in Fig. 9 as a representative example. The reciprocal of the slopes of these lines are called the throwing index I_{throw} and represent a measure of bath throwing power²⁶.

Figs. 9(a,b) reveal the throwing power for nickel and cobalt from the optimum plating bath which to 3.4 and 49.02% respectively for the bath which enriched with citrate (Cit : Ac = 2 : 1) while the other bath (Cit : Ac = 1 : 2) gives to 60 and 13.82% respectively.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Fig. 10 cyclic voltammograms for Co-Ni alloy deposition/dissolution in optimum bath composition :

- (a) 10 g/L CoSO_4 , 20 g/L NiSO_4 , 40 g/L NaSO_4 , 40 g/L sodium citrate and 20 g/L sodium acetate.
- (b) 40 g/L CoSO_4 , 30 g/L NiSO_4 , 40 g/L NaSO_4 , 20 g/L sodium citrate and 40 g/L sodium acetate.

The cathodic peak appears at somewhat different potentials, that is, 224.788 and 345.438 mV, respectively.

It is clearly observed that; by increasing the ratio of

Fig. 9(a). Relation between metal distribution ratio (M) and linear ratio (L) for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6, deposition time = 35 min and 45°C .

Fig. 9(b). Relation between metal distribution ratio (M) and linear ratio (L) for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (10 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (40 gL^{-1}), current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6, deposition time = 35 min and 45°C .

Fig. 10. Cyclic voltammogram for cobalt-nickel alloy deposition on glassy carbon electrode in cobalt sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (30 gL^{-1}), sodium sulphate (40 gL^{-1}), pH = 6, with different complexing agent ratio : [a] sodium citrate = 40 g dm^{-3} and [b] sodium acetate = 20 g dm^{-3} , 20 mV s^{-1} at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

acetate in the bath, the cathodic peak shifts to more negative which reflect that the deposition process getting more difficult. This is referring to the fact both cobalt and nickel form more stable complexes with acetate with respect to citrate ones.

Crystal structure and surface morphology of the deposits :

X-Ray diffraction data obtained for as-deposited cobalt-nickel alloy shows that by increasing the citrate ratio in the bath the whole system is change completely due to the appearance of new planes as shown in Figs. 11, 12.

The finding planes in low citrate ratio are 002 and 312 with high intensity and the system is closed packed hexagonal (Fig. 11) while by increasing citrate ratio in the bath, there are additional planes obtained beside the two planes, are 410, 330, 331, 311, 602 and 532; and the intensity of the main peaks getting lower. And the system changes to be tetragonal (Fig. 12).

In the presence of saccharin the system is independent on the citrate ratio in the bath, and it is closed packed hexagonal (CPH) system but the intensity of the planes getting relatively higher. While in the presence of thiourea, also the same system is given (CPH system) but the

Fig. 11. X-Ray diffraction for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (10 gL^{-1}), nickel sulfate (20 gL^{-1}), sodium sulfate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium acetate (40 gL^{-1}), sodium citrate (20 gL^{-1}), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm^{-2}), pH = 6 and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Closed-packed hexagonal system (CPR) : (a) No additives, (b) In the presence of 0.5 g L^{-1} saccharin, (c) In the presence of 1 g L^{-1} thiourea.

intensity of peaks decreased by increasing citrate ratio in the plating bath.

Figs. 13, 14 show the scanning electron micrographs for the electrodeposited Co-Ni alloys in the presence and absence of additives from different citrate : acetate ratios baths. It is clearly observed that the percentage of citrate or acetate in the bath have no essential effect on the morphology of the deposit either in free additives solutions or in the presence of additives such as saccharin or thiourea. In all cases, the obtained deposit is columnar but it

Fig. 12. X-Ray diffraction for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (40 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²), pH = 6 and 25 C°. Tetragonal system : a = 8.85, b = -, c = 4.59; (a) No additives, (b) In the presence of 0.5 g L⁻¹ saccharin, (c) In the presence of 1 g L⁻¹ thiourea.

is very compact in absence of additives while in their presence there is relatively larger inter columnar spaces due to the blocking of some active sites by the action of additives.

Mechanism of cathodic reduction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes from electrolytes containing acetate and citrate as a complexing agents :

(i) The electrodeposition of nickel-cobalt alloys followed by a local pH rise near the electrode surface results in the formation of strongly citrate complexes, NiCit(HCit)³⁻ and Co₂Cit₂⁴⁻, that are electrochemically inactive.

These complexes are involved in the chemical reactions :

Fig. 13. Scanning electron micrographs for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (10 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²), pH = 6 and at 25 C° in the absence and presence of additives : [a] No additives, [b] In the presence of 0.5 g L⁻¹ saccharin, [c] In the presence of 1 g L⁻¹ thiourea.

The single charged protonated citrate complexes may adsorb on the electrode surface either through a delocalized proton of citrate or via substitution by bridging through a desorbed SO₄²⁻.

Fig. 14. Scanning electron micrographs for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (40 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²), p.i = 6 at 25 °C in the absence and presence of additives : [a] No additives, [b] In the presence of 0.5 g L⁻¹ saccharin, [c] In the presence of 1 g L⁻¹ thiourea.

Further increase in cathodic polarization would be followed by conversion of chelate Ni(HCit)⁻ and Co(HCit)⁻ complexes to the surface bridge-structure complex with an internal delocalized proton [M_x-H-Cit-Ni(II)]_s^σ and [M_x-H-Cit-Co(II)]_s^σ.

(ii) In addition; the possibility of the formation of heteronuclear complex in the vicinity of the electrode or

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (10 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (20 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.432 A dm⁻²), pH 6 and at 25 C°

Position	Area	Crystal size	Microstrain	RMS strain
In absence of additives :				
44.59459	73.07223	90.9	0.1	0.1
64.89609	16.42717	68.2	0.1	0.1
82.26217	20.89652	78.8	0.1	0.1
98.89426	4.863915	138.3	0.1	0.1
In the presence of saccharin (0.5 gL ⁻¹) :				
44.84	91.46308	99.8	0.1	0.1
65.16164	21.39816	70.2	0.1	0.1
82.48164	24.4846	101	0.1	0.1
99.08995	4.573094	109.6	0.1	0.1
In the presence of thiourea (1.0 gL ⁻¹) :				
44.83321	90.8099	98.1	0.1	0.1
65.13825	18.2893	58.2	0.1	0.1
82.49065	19.06495	103	0.1	0.1
99.07102	5.283405	94.9	0.1	0.1

Table 3. X-Ray diffraction for the electrodeposition of cobalt-nickel alloy from bath containing cobalt sulfate (40 gL⁻¹), nickel sulfate (30 gL⁻¹), sodium sulphate (40 gL⁻¹), sodium acetate (20 gL⁻¹), sodium citrate (40 gL⁻¹), deposition time = 35 min, current density (0.864 A dm⁻²), pH 6 and at 25 C°

Position	Area	Crystal size	Microstrain	RMS strain
In absence of additives :				
41.49675	24.50513	31.6	0.1	0.1
44.52525	31.67435	29.9	0.1	0.1
47.15606	13.88526	15.8	0.1	0.1
75.72191	14.73332	29.1	0.1	0.1
82.10869	13.98881	39.4	0.1	0.1
In the presence of saccharin (0.5 gL ⁻¹) :				
44.8284	94.75881	86.4	0.1	0.1
65.13257	21.20959	63.7	0.1	0.1
82.49089	20.82517	98.9	0.1	0.1
99.12062	6.760379	55.9	0.1	0.1
In the presence of thiourea (1.0 gL ⁻¹) :				
44.87474	82.81404	94.6	0.1	0.1
65.2121	22.46535	17.4	0.1	0.1
82.50556	29.29922	76.4	0.1	0.1
99.08079	3.709923	115.4	0.1	0.1

on its surface cannot be ruled out, such intermediate surface complex would favor the electrodeposition of Ni-Co alloy in electrolytes containing citrate anions.

The reduction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complex may be schematically presented :

As mentioned above, a plethora of experimental result of Ni-Co alloy deposition shows an anomalous electrochemical behavior regardless of the anion composition of the electrolyte. This has provided further support to the experimental evidence that they are considered as complexing agents, although improving stabilization of solution and completely bonding the less noble metal, are not sufficient effective at reducing anomalous codeposition.

These observations point to the fact that, the inhibiting of the discharge rate of the nobler component is likely to depend on the internal structural feature of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} species involved in the reduction process.

To explain the anomalous codeposition of Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ let us consider the individual complexes from the standpoint of crystal theory :

Cobalt possesses the electronic structure 3d⁷, 4s². Nickel has the electronic structure 3d⁸ 4s². In the light of this theory, aqua- and protonated citrate Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ complexes can be related to coordinative substances, whose structures show little sublevel splitting, namely, high-spin complexes.

Calculated crystal field stabilization energy for Ni²⁺ octahedral complexes are 29.3 and 17.1 kcal for Co²⁺.

High-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes with three unpaired electrons are more labile than that of Ni^{II}. Therefore they are expected to react rapidly, and they have been observed to do so. We believe that the formation of labile high-spin cobalt complexes would explain preferential reduction of Co²⁺ as compared with Ni²⁺[28].

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